

Review Article

Review paper on resistance drugs problem of antiamoebiasis Drugs, Current status, Research needs and Opportunity for proesses

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ABSTRACT

Amoebiasis caused by Entamoeba histolytica parasite disease are growing in poor and developing countries. There are lots of issue regarding cure of such disease. so, non-selective use of anti-amoebic drugs can cause of increased minimum inhibitory concentration against Entamoeba. histolytica parasite. The limited number of drugs of antiamoebics drugs available. so, a new approach to treat such as Entamoeba histolytica parasitic disease. In future, the development of drugs resistance may cause seriously affect the control of disease. This review discusses current status, research needs and opportunity.

INTRODUCTION

Amoebiasis is the second leading cause of death from parasitic disease worldwide. The causative agent Entamoeba histolytica is one of the most common parasitic infections worldwide, infecting about 50 million people and resulting in 40,000-100,000 deaths a year. Secreting proteinases that dissolve host tissues, killing host cells on contact, and engulfing red blood cells, E histolytica trophozoites invade the intestinal mucosa, causing amoebic colitis. In some cases amoebas breach the

mucosal barrier and travel through the portal circulation to the liver, where they cause abscesses consisting of a few E histolytica trophozoites surrounding dead and dying hepatocytes and liquefied cellular debris. Amoebic liver abscesses grow inexorably and, at one time, were almost always fatal, but now even large abscesses can be cured by one dose of antibiotic. Evidence that what we thought was a single species based on morphology is, in fact, two genetically distinct species--now termed Entamoeba histolytica (the

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pathogen) and *Entamoeba dispar* (a commensal) - has turned conventional wisdom about the epidemiology and diagnosis of amoebiasis upside down. New models of disease have linked *E. histolytica* induction of intestinal inflammation and hepatocyte programmed cell death to the pathogenesis of amoebic colitis and amoebic liver abscess [1][2][3].

The people at risk of infection include immigrants, travellers returning from countries of high endemicity, Indigenous people, and men who have sex with men. Clinical manifestations range from asymptomatic carriage to invasive disease. Amoebic colitis and amoebic liver abscess are the most common invasive manifestations observed. Treatment should always include a luminal agent to eradicate colonization, prevent spread and/or reduce the risk of invasive disease. [6][7]

Fig.1- Life cycle of *Entamoeba histolytica*

Antiamoebic drugs

The parasite *E. histolytica* is capable of acquiring resistance to amoebicidal concentrations of metronidazole (MTZ), the current drug of choice, under laboratory conditions, and this drug resistance has been associated with an increased expression of iron-containing superoxide dismutase and peroxiredoxin. Moreover, partial resistance to MTZ has also been described in some clinical strains of *E. histolytica*, suggesting the emergence of MTZ resistant strains [7]. Thus, these

observations have led to the search for new drugs with targets with different mode of action.

Classification of antiamoebic drugs

Antiamoebic drugs are classified into three groups luminal, tissue and mixed amoebicides. metronidazole is major drugs of choice and other nitroimidazole derived compound like tinidazole, ornidazole is used in amoebic disease. diloxanide furoate, emetine, chloroquine also used as alternative drugs in amoebic disease. Chloroquine could be used along with metronidazole in cause of hepatic amoebiasis.

Drug mechanism of *E. histolytica*

Resistance in clinical isolates is less defined in biochemical terms because parasite populations are often heterogenous. Parasite may evade drug action by hiding in sanctuaries. So far the mechanisms of drug resistance hypothesized in protozoan parasite are decrease of drug uptake because of loss of a transporter required for uptake, the efflux of drugs from the parasite either by the P-glycoproteins (Pgp) or by ATPases, the alteration of drug target, and loss of drug activation. Metronidazole and related nitroimidazole, tinidazole (which is not available in some countries), are the only effective drugs for the treatment of trichomoniasis and giardiasis. In the latter cases, clinical resistance to these drugs has been documented. Laboratory induced

metronidazole resistance in *E. histolytica* has been reported and metronidazole resistant *E. histolytica* strains have been maintained indefinitely in medium. Metronidazole and related nitroimidazole, tinidazole (which is not available in some countries), are the only effective drugs for the treatment of trichomoniasis and giardiasis. In the latter cases, clinical resistance to these drugs has been documented. Laboratory induced metronidazole resistance in *E. histolytica* has been reported and metronidazole resistant *E. histolytica* strains have been maintained indefinitely in medium^[8].

Table no.1: Limitation of current classes of antiameboebic

Sr.no	Current drugs	Toxicity	Resistance
1	Metronidazole	peripheral neuropathy, stiff joints, hepatic renal insufficiency (nephrotoxicity), cardiotoxicity, accumulate inside the tissues, such as particularly in liver and spleen, etc.	A high metronidazole resistance rate (17.5%) seen in the current study
2	Tinidazole	Dizziness, tremor, poor coordination, seizure, vertigo etc.	Resistance of tinidazole is (9.7%) seen
3	Ornidazole	Headache, dry in the mouth, nausea and a slight metallic taste in the mouth	Resistance forming helicobacter pylori resistance etc.

The models available to study the mechanism of drug resistance in *E. Histolytica* include in vitro induced metronidazole resistant cell lines of *E. histolytica* and emetine resistant mutant clones derived from virulent HM1: IMSS strain, which was selected after mutagenesis with alkylating agent, ethyl methanesulphonate. Expression of iron containing superoxide dismutase (fe-SOD) and peroxiredoxin has been shown to be increased three to five-fold in metronidazole resistant parasites and this has been confirmed at the gene expression level with decrease in the expression of ferredoxin and flavin reductase. The critical involvement of fe-SOD and peroxiredoxin was confirmed by episomal transfection of these antioxidant enzymes into metronidazole susceptible isolates, which was associated with

reduced drug susceptibility. The metronidazole are also lacking and therefore the antiamebic susceptibility of pathogenic clinical isolates needs to be investigated to help in developing strategies to increase the efficacy and the life span of the limited number of currently available antiamebic drugs^{[8][9][10]}.

CONCLUSION

In view of the lack of safe drugs and the serious secondary effects caused. There is a need for new drugs for the treatment of amebiasis infections. The discovery of novel classes of inhibitors can be an important step which contributes to overcoming the drug resistance of amebiasis. Therefore, development of novel, effective, and safe antiamebiasis agents, with reduced side effects, is a major priority.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No Potential conflict of interest relevant to this article was reported.

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